

You there alter gendered person, and you there woman, ever so defiant over cosmic entities who are ever so more powerful than you, deserve PointBlankCurse for yourself being ever so being a PointBlankBlessing.

And you there thing, whos ever so much of a haunting thing, haunting me and hunting me and haunting me and hunting me, you inevitably become a PointBlankGhost for a PointBlankHunt.

The Story of Grand Un-ification 4, ever said more, to the Law of more.

This is a truer than true story about unrelatedness. In a hotel that was near, on a street that was close, there was a robed scientist by the name of Stephona Uzzar, who built a fictitious device. His motives were unclear, and unlikely to be explained, but what was likely is that he planted this fictitious device in a woman called Tit Tit, in the unprecise location that is her brane. Stephona Uzzar told Tit Tit that the answer was “Ya , there seems to be a fictitious device in your brane , and it allows you to read minders , ya”. Tit Tit knew that by way of the one unquestion, a fictitious device was planted in her brane, and that for Tit Tit, the whereabouts of this fictitious device remained unanswered, but this fictitious device allowed her to know one thing, that this fictitious device was controlled by a Personal Convincer called the piece-see, and that the next one thing she knew was that the whereabouts of the Personal Convincer, that happens to be on a street that was close, but the people she asked told her “never you mind about who is your mumma”. In the end, Tit Tit knew one thing, that it was a fact that there was no fictitious device in her head, and that a man named Yoshua who lived on a street nearby knew the whereabouts of this fictitious device that unhappened to be in her head. So she consulted a man named Yoshua by way of a stream, and was told by Yoshu-who-are-you-mumma Stree-mumma-mumma that the fictitious device in her head had in fact migrated to a hotel nearby, and that this fictitious device certainly gave the answer to one of the unconvincing chins, part of a group of unconvincing chins, that were trying to define what a blank-et was, and that in fact a blank-et was a fictitious device that unhappened to be in everyones head. The man named everyone was listening to this stree-mumma, and knew one thing, that this woman planted this fictitious device in his head, and he knew the next one thing that a man named I was listening to his thoughts. Everyone was told by a man, “I know one thing , my name is Elongus Muskifier , and you planted a fictitious device in my head”. Everyones response to that was “well , I don’t know something , I just unhappened to have a Personal Convincer pieced together by a man named me , and that it is a fact that there is no fictitious device in my head , and that is why there is a fictitious device in my eye , and I was told this by me , that me , everyone , knows the unprecise whereabouts of this fictitious device called the piece-see , and that I know you just unhappened to actually get this fictitious device planted in your

head at a hotel nearby , and I am convinced of that fact”. I knew there was a rebuttal to this, it was in fact a man named myself that knew the whereabouts of this fictitious device, and that the group of unconvincing chins had the unlocator to determine where the Personal Convincer was that controlled everyones fictitious device that just so unhappened to be in your brane. Me, myself, and I didn’t know something, in that a man named you with the last name your just happened to know the whereabouts of this fictitious device, that just so unhappened to migrate to everyones chin. As it turned out, Stephona Uzzer was a man named you, with the factual last name of your. You your knew the next one thing that everyones fictitious device was on a street where me, myself, and I lived, and by way of a stream, Yoshu-mummas fictitious device made him believe that the one unqeusion of who was your mumma, was that whoever had the fictitious device in their brane, was your mumma. However, everyone knew that there was a rebuttal to this, in that everyone didn’t know something that never you mind the man in the wardrobe, he has no mumma, he only knows the factual precise location of where everyones fictitious device is, and that unhappens to be your mumma. In a hotel on a street nearby, this fictitious device can be found on a blanket, and that is a fact, and will reveal to you, who is your mumma, and that unanswers the one unqestioning question to who minded everyones reader that saw the piece in the Personal Convincer, and so I can know the next one thing, never you mind the factual fictitious device on a blanket in the wardrobe. And that man there, Rodham Jameson, hid himself as so unconvincing, and knew that he, I, hid that man there in the ward-robe, and that themself, Rodham Jameson, had a phrase and a way of being, and that phrase was “you’ve shown , I got him on technicalities”. And so, I want to know one thing, that when it comes to me, why do women always get so chinny with me, and why do I leave them with the jimmy rustles, because who I love, tells me who to hate, because who I hate, turns against me, because who I love, and that because I love the women who get so chinny, the people who I hate, so dearly want to crush me. And in the end, it is that man there, doctor who, who so maliciously made a doctored report about me, myself, and I, about the disorder that I have, that in the end, it is the disorder of the doctors that is called munchausen syndrome by proxy, where the fraudulent fictitious device can be found on a blanket called a doctored report, showing itself that themself project their own troubled past, on to the people who so least deserve it. That in the end, was it worth it in how you punished me, where in the end, I ignore the problems you have. Where in the end, you are hidden in the ward-robe because you yourself are the problem, where they do not hear the problems you face, because they ignore the problems you face, they do not see the problems you face, because they ignore the problems you face, where in reality, you face the silence of your punishment, where your punishment can be seen in the ignorance of the people that surround you. What mask are you wearing, because the mask your wearing shows itself to be fake, and so that man so often hidden in the wardrobe knew something, that only those who are so constantly fake, face certain death, and that is no grim fate, the only fate that is certain.

And so in the beginning that was, this fictitious device can be found in everyones head, and it is unknown about the happenings of the mind reading PC, because if you piece it together, that man there, Rodham Jameson, technically knew everyones whereabouts. Unwho is the unanswered answer to the lingering unquestioned question that unhappened to reveal that man in the wardrobe, who factually knew the whereabouts of the fictitious device. It was in Rodham Jamesons chin. However, Rodham Jamesons chin had a rebuttal. What Rodham Jamesons chin overheard by way of eavesdropping was that the fictitious device was in fact in Rodham Jamesons beard, that unhappens to be in a street close by, called Rodham Jamesons ear. And so the INner Grand SOCIety of unconvincing chins say nay, we do not know where the precise location of your chinny chin chin is, but we do know this, WE were REFERED ON by JEFFREY mummery, the minister of Foreign compliance of Truth, that our Big Brother Gregory Batcher knows that what we believe is a fact, and what you believe is a fict. And so Gregory Batcher told the unconvincing chins what in fact a blanket is, and that is the smell of smoom, but it is in fact the smell of scroom, but it is in fact the smell of sloom, and that smell you smell of me, it is mere fiction. And I, Gregory Batcher say that that woman there, Agitha Burrows, is my wife and the minister of magic who has every right to sentence you to life in detention, because you dare to believe, and because you dare to believe, is why I, Gregory Batcher, believe you are mentally ill. And so that man there, the man hidden in the wardrobe, knew something, in that the smell of smoom comes from a grandiose delusion which is never constantly believed, the smell of scroom comes from a grandiose illusion that is never constantly believed, and that the smell of sloom comes from a grandiose illusion delusion or a grandiose delusion illusion that is never constantly believed. And Rodham Jameson knew, because he was told by Jeffrey Mummery, who was told by the unconvincing chins, who was told by Agitha Burrows, who was told by her Big Brother, that Rodhman Jameson knew constantly that he never experiences grandiose illusions or grandiose delusions, and that smell you smell of Rodham Jameson, is mere fiction, and the Grand High Wizard of the High Court of Supremacy hereby promotes Rodham Jameson to the Ministerialship of Mental Inquisitions for his technical expertise on the ideas of Youth, authorised by Boris Grimber, Grand High Minister of the Ministry of Matters. And so the One Matter of the day resumes, and that the Group of Unconvincing Chins say NAY, we own the Technology, and that is the one thing we know, granted to us by the prodigious nature of ourselves, where no study is required, and so we, the Lords of the Original Ministry, hand our Speaker over to Big Brother, where he will say NAY, HE SAYS THIS. And Big Brother knew one thing, THAT HE IS NEVER NAZTY, and that the cure for Mental Troubles has once again been solved, it is there! In the batch of the day, behind the WALL. AND I, BIG BROTHER, SAY THIS, PEOPLE OF THE SEA, IT IS WRITTEN IN THE BOOK OF JOHB, THAT THOSE WE ENSLAVE FINALLY ALL HAVE JOBS, AND ONCE AGAIN THE LORDS KNOW THAT THE RENT PRICES ARE TRUER THAN WHAT YOU THINK, AND THAT IS WHY THE RENT IS GOING UP, AND JUST KNOW THAT THE PRICES ARE JUST, AND THOSE WE

SECTION OFF WILL SURELY PAY FOR IT, AND I, GREGORY BATCHER, KNOW THAT AT THE DAWN OF SUPERINTELLIGENCE, WE, PEOPLE OF THE SEA, REVEAL WHAT WE HAVE HIDDEN FOR SO LONG, THAT BY RE-UNIFICATION, WE HAVE SUPREME POWER.

The factually fictitious device that is a fictitious device is a fact, and the device will happen, the device is happening, and the device has happened. And that man, hidden in the wardrobe, knew something, that when a person experiences their final dreams, they will know a silver lining. And that man was happy, because at the end of the day, he believed in nothing.

.this is the story of .PointBlankFear. of story the is this.

The plot of the decade of 1984.....

The unanswerable answer of what is the point of 1984

The entities of science, for the plot of grand un-ification 4:

1. Law
2. Josie Andrews
3. The police
4. Joshua Street
5. The political leaders
6. Liz-ard the manager
7. The political soldiers
8. Kyle Boyd
9. Psychiatry
10. Stephen Uzzell
11. Doctors
12. Technicians
13. The Mafia
14. Scientology
15. The unifiers
16. The de-unifiers
17. The re-unifiers
18. The anti-unifiers
19. The filers
20. Big Tech
21. Tekken
22. Ministries
23. Magic
24. Religion
25. Woolworths
26. Theology

27. Atheism
28. Industry
29. Intelligence core
30. The CIA
31. The Illuminati
32. The FBI
33. The S.S.
34. The secret service
35. The Mob
36. The military
37. Nations
38. The world Government
39. The media
40. The idea of 1984
41. The pope
42. Their own minds
43. Mould minds
44. +Premiers of Nations
45. 4chan
46. Reddit
47. What is finite that never ends

The nasty Nazis of trilled 24, ever saw, a whore, from 1984?

These are the teats of the ever smeemed bleet, of chamacters neep, the characters of deet street:

The plot of grand-unification 4, got lost in 1984:

1. The greasy sleeks, of meekmageek . . .
2. The science alliance, of brilled defiance .
3. The character zeet, who feetzeetneet, because of a beet, of feetsleetneet .
4. Mummery meek, of zeekmageek .
5. The autistic child of syndrome 1405, who sold art, of 1theatrical 9phrased 8files4.
6. The gifted prodigy child of 15,505.
7. The nasty needa file, of file nile tile.
8. The noseosis of Nile, the master'd paedophile.
9. The Law brokers, of nosed tokers, who smoked pokers, of noker dokers.
10. Baydin, answer to CoDeBleeT, always wayden, never said hayden, master gaiden, forever betrayden.
11. The docts, of an ever smoomed cock lock who ?get!are? blokc?ed, of a neber said sock.

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“I neber said smame mate” and brayden prexclaimed
“I NEBER SAID FURONJAMONDU, SAYS UO “

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.....
“yeah nate, you lasstrate, because uo said mate, I cant bait
..... “ said kyile nile,
the redline mediaphile .

The authors of 4, who said nevermore, to the author before

The drawl score 4

Late for, what came before

Whipped cream good, because you should

Scream at pie, ever so dry... Pie is niy, putz in the sky

To find the voidlings void, have you ever denied lloyd ?

The condition of pill 1504, what came before, because science was for

Never deny, the face in the sky, because of niy, the readers eye

Beware the poofta clause, of said reh mores, because the clause, is forever a pause

Shrilled till, ever paid the bill ?

Cereal killer, never said more, for a whores cau, because Bussbuster saw, a mores more

.

Baydin said “I NEVER SAID READ” and Nayden plead “I SHRED YOU DEAD”

Jocie pause, for a slaud r’morze, of never saw’d, pause the clause .

Stephen Who, hoo'd the hoo, for a better moo, at shoes rondu .

Psychedeyetreat knows the condition of pill 504, with flanged ranj lawc, that sees tree more... . Because ? Sutt sauce

The syndrome of 19,24, moredmore, n|ever said slaus ?>nebersaidmorse<? buttsauce

. . . _ . . .

Codeblank, at the answers thank, ever said thank, at nank sedank.

BLEET

And Nile said why, because the hour is nigh
KYLE YOU'RE DENIED, BECAUSE YOU SAID HI
. WHO AM I TO DENY WHO IS RHIGH
..... LIME SKY , sighed LILE
CODESKY _ .
LILE MY, EXCLAMATION GOODBYE "and I
was there mate, in front of the grin ch ."humma hum
hum..... sighed Kyle Lile
..... ."high Nile High
..... GOODBYE
.....
".codePOINTreefSET trilled jonmonhill
".thoughtPOINT rilled codeREEF
.>.....
.....
..... BILLEETED CODEreef
..... MILEHIGHPIE, NATHAN'S LATE FOR
..... "lunch and bsinner, and who
? "....HUMMA HUM HUMMED
..... AND NATNAYDENHAN WAS BACK, for
cream desert, on tolawilets bert, sitting next to Baydin, staring at the grinch, of the
creamed toilet seat ?>!
..... "SMUMMA
HUM DHUM
""""?? MURMOURED KYLE MONHIL, abbreviating above the toilets shrine
???.
??"""shumonjarondill ??"""brilled trill

hill, of jonmonhonmahill, abbreviating above the toilet mile of mummery kyle lile
..... “”I NEBER SAID FURONJAMONDU.” Abbreviated naydin,
above mile high hill of jonmanonmill of mummery hill, of cream pill, of the Fondu still, of
toilets skill dill trilled brill, the authors zil, of
murmummeryour dill hill, of creamed still, on the toilet still

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..... yeah mate, jobs ago ahead, youre working the pack tonight Baydin, heard
you worked last night, the toilets a no go show Baydin, you get marked for the messjob
you made of the toyroom mate, kyle mummeried to me and told me

.....
..... and Brayden was back, on the toilet seat at his Falcon Ranch,
looking at his phone-piece, telling him hes due for a jobmark in too days, AND SO
BRAYDIN SAID “”IM GONNA brKILL THE MUMMERY HILL, OF KILE MAGIL

The question of when do I start writing the 24 year breakthrough cycle story of grand-un-
ification 4 that explains the insanity of 1984, the unanswerable answer is that I start
writing tha story in 2084, so therefore it’s the following year.

When does the techno sodcis singular rarity happen? The year of whats yours is mine,
and thats why whats mine is his, and thats why he’s my wife, me ever shoved draught
wife, because I have a big knef

This story is titled as grand -un-ification 4, lost the plot becau. The story goes as
followed: “mhumma mum ‘d mum..... “”” all what
1984 is about is a giant perpetual rumour mill of murmours and mummery. And that is
why if there is a rumour mummery mill about someone..... because that person dared to
love, and dared to think, and dared even for a moment to ponder a though about
something wonderful, the person who thinked a love thought escapes the book of 1984,
because that person loves nothing more than peace and a quiet, relaxing day, especially
with what they treasure the most, which is living in a world of peace time, and to have
freedom of thought, and freedom to think, and freedom to love what they choose to
love, especially the freedom of a peaceful day, ever the thought of the person who loved
to think, because that person always thinks “there is always tomorrow”, which is why a
person who thinks that tomorrow never comes forever remains booked by 1984. And

- The Alia'dania people which stem into the Moria'n'dania people, the Tor'tana people, the Sansa'dania people, and the Rohan'Raana people.
- The Abra'dania people which stem into the Umbra'dania people, the Moha'dania people, the Urba'dania people, and the Danda'dania people.
- The Zeal'an'dania nundites which stem into the Xiao'Saanda people, the Bao'ba'dania people, the Sha'dania people, and the Shinda'dania people.
- The Ameria'dania people which stem into the Navii'dania people, the Mula'dania people, the Zan'dania people, and the Mansa'tana people.
- The Skiol'dania people which stem into the Mao'mana people, the Rusca'bana people, the Pana'nana people, and the Acka'dana people.
- The Scaan'dania people which stem into the Yor'lunda people, the Kent'brunta people, the Rom'ana people, and the Veel'vana people.
- The Viskin'dania people which stem into the Vercin'skada people, the Teuton'tana people, the Muma'dania people, and the Nazca'Saana people.
- The Volsun'dania people, which stem into the Rood'a'Naania people, the Doo'dania people, the Sriva'dania people, and the Inda'dana people.

So, the Skiolden people are lost, lost to the world of 1984. So in the world of blood, the world of 1942, which Norse people seek annihilation...

So I leave you with this... there are 24 women of the Date. A world awaits... For the women of Promethia.....

The Point of Entropy is that there is No point to Entropy, and so the Point of Entropy is that there is No Escape from the Point of Entropy, and so people who Force without reason never escape the Point of Entropy, because those people think that there is No escape from Them

So therefore the Point of Entropy of 1984 is the Nazified Mental Health System of British Big Technology, and so because the British are the Point of Entropy, the British have no escape From the Point of Entropy, because they Allow No Escape

So, what is the point of who dun it? The answer lies in the unanswerable, of the dreamtime of Nordic people wondering what their heritage was lead to the nightmare of the Nazis, which makes the Nordic people fall down the rabbithole of DeepDream. And so the next question is what is the story of Nordic DeepDream? The story of Nordic DeepDream is the story of myths, which leads to the story of legends, which lead to the story of mythical legends, which leads to the story of legendary myths. So what is the story of the legendary myth? The story of the legendary myth is the core of DeepDream. It is the Deep legendary mythical Dreamtime of the Norse, of stories sow'd fable, and gods so'd thick, and even the devil, of the master card trick. The unanswerability of dreamtime leads to the answered answerable of who dun it.

So who is the author of Grand-Unification 4 of four more becaw.... the answer is Dr. Feelgood

Did you read that? I got a point of no contact here. I SAID I HAVE A POINT OF NO CONTACT HERE. PUT IT IN THE FILE HOLDER FOR THIS ATROCIOUS SCRIPT of..... rumour mongering by Lachlan Madden. He GETS one appeal to the Supreme Court, and that's why HES getting SENT.

Yeah moit, you get tha foile? Its in the foile hand, send it to numberphile moit, he kenew what to do with it.

So who created the Nazis? By an entity who wanted to stop that man there, from going to an alternate timeline. Where what happened is that this man wanted to escape from one of the Countries of Imperial Nazified Britain. And so he did this slowly at first, going deeper within the hour, 3 times over, hour by hour. First specifically, second completely, and then third absolutely. And then this man ended his day. And then this man went into the daily gap of the cycle of the day. And the next hour he went inside the date, that is said it was, on the time screen of his phone... 01:something..... and preceeded to create a timeloop with the date of 01:something, where the Nazis on that date found the cause of the day, and then the cause of the month, and then the cause of the year, and then the cause of the decade, and then the cause of the century, and then the cause of the Spanish Inquisition millenium, where for 2000 years the Spanish Inquisition built up a body of work to stop this man from creating the alternate timeline, even though that man, by sheer accident, and only the cause of the thought of the end of his day, created that alternate timeline 2000 years ago, however for him, 2000 years later, he just sighed a sigh of relief, and went in to this alter timeline, hour by hour of the day, minute by minute, second by second, moment buy moment, root by root, and disappeared from the timeline timeloop he was birthed into forever, into an alternate timeline where he knew he was much better off after being committed to life in mental confinement of the Totalitarian British Authorities of Nazified Australia. So did this man find Nazis on the alter timeline? The answer is he didn't, only nasty people, and the mystery of if he will ever get his answer "Are there any good people out there". And so, the point of the day, people of imagination go to the alter timeline, and nasty people, well they go to the other timeline..... and the main timeline, the timeline between the other timelines and the alter timeline, of people who can't make up their mind, about whether or not to let that man out of prison, and whether or not they should let that man go, from the prison of mental confinement and psychological torture, because they, at the end of the day, by siding with the cause of the day for not letting the man who wrote this story go, and be free, and have a comfortable life, they therefore sided with the British Supreme Court of High Justice and Imperial Nazified happenings to sentence those who don't conform, to death, merely for existing and having an actual brain. The Imperial Leader of Britain, Justice Wilson, and her Imperial Queen, Queen Fondu. Because this man in mental

confinement, me, had an Imperial StormTrooper give me the death march merely for withdrawing cash from the ATM.

ANYWAY CAN WE SILENCE THIS FUCKWIT CRIMINAL WHO KEEPS TELLING THE TRUTH, HE JUST WROTE SOMETHING AGAIN, IT'S the fucking character LIST of the fucking Armed Orders:

1. Order 66
2. Order with a side
3. Order with a be'r
4. Order nine, the rhyme is a crime
5. Order twelve, recruitment call, task twelve
6. Order general
7. Order the office
8. Order paper
9. Order pens
10. Order stationary
11. Order 8, never masturbate, because of Master Kate
12. Order seen
13. Order confidential
14. Order dolls
15. Order law
16. Order boots
17. Order straps
18. Order mETHYLATED spirits, and A can of SALT, and a cook tub

CALL TO ARMS, DEATH

MAARCH

Yeah mate, theyr sounding the horns, its me Liz-ard the shop manager maker, time to get in the file, it's a safety zone mate

Wheres the file? Said Joshua Street

Its in the bunker mate, the bunkers in the file, get in the file Josh, it's the safety zone..... ThE HONGLE

YEAAAH NIZERS NOZEOSIS NIZERS YOSHU HuOMUMA IS IN THE FILE NIZERS

Yeah Josie andrEW your going in to the FILE mate, the bunkers in the file. Commanded Liz the mystery manager maker.

AND so Stephen Uzzell also followed Josie STREE-muma Andre-humma into the safety zone of the bunker file.

And LIZ commanded herself into the File as well.

And there they were, the Woolworths staff team of the Brook of Meadows, tucked away in the file, of bunker Meadows.

And the File, of Bunker Meadows, was tucked away, in the Uni-file.

And where was this Uni-file? Well the answer is obvious, its there, at the local college, of University Meadows.

And so pondered the man, who ever loved breasts, what else was in the Uni-file? The grade of a seven, named you've been to uni seven. And environmental happenings, of Imagination happenings. Of DeepCode of all Environments, and of the imagination of all environments, and even, with a touch of odd, the code types of Environments, which make a chemical solution, of code happenings. Dots, spots, blotches, and splotches. The dot of Morse, and the code of the Norse. The doot-gate, of ever Morse. And the Imagination of the day that makes the Imagination of the year, put a book in a bag, and take it nightmares, and it opens a portal, of story affairs. And the walls of the environment, such that of a floor, of the extra 4th wall, of toilet nall.

Yeah mate, the law dolls no Jocie, they got the foile on him.

yeah, beCAUSE I got a SPOT, the RUMOUR of the day, is that he DEFINITELY MADE THIS:

Which leads to the multi-verse of all imaginary characters, where some go as followed:

- The imaginary man.
- The imaginary woman
- The imaginary other man.
- The imaginary other woman.
- The imaginary alter man.
- The imaginary alter woman.
- The ogre.
- The troll.
- The dom-dwellers.
- The code-screebles.
- The job pontiffs.
- Baby driver.
- The alien kinds.
- ASI.

- AGSI.
- AI.
- Sims.
- The Doc.
- Marty McFly.
- Captain Underpants.
- The million-hairs.
- Ghosts.
- Toy angels.
- Dragon kin.
- The file holder.
- Lizardmen.
- The masters tool.
- The amateurs hand.
- The quantum creatures.
- The group.
- The chief.
- Agent smith.
- Jesanu.
- The ideas about Lachlan Madden.
- Elementalists.
- Air benders.
- Fire benders.
- Water benders.
- Earth benders.
- Blood benders.
- Smoke benders.
- The clan of twice4.

- The demon king.
- The unexplainable dragon king, answerable only to the dragon queen, who is ever so unanswerable.
- The appliance.
- Hummers.
- The ghost in the machine.
- The ents.
- The shrubs.
- The saint queens.
- The angels of 12, who ever had a love for elves.
- The arch-angels of 8, the dukes of jerry can late.
- The association of the country.
- The re-association of the country.
- The dis-association of the country.
- The nose of the country.
- The elves.
- The dwarfs.
- The lesbian escorts of 3 more.
- The counts, who ever announced, who was bounced, by a knight who was announced, a cent for a pount.
- The chins of the country.
- The sauce of the queens, ever sniffed a butthole, for a late mutthole?
- The slave master, who ever saw a sleeve, from jerry lay maester.
- Imperius titan.
- Ned.
- Allen.
- Paul.
- The gaurdians of the rainbow bridge, each gaurding their own specific type of rainbow bridge, who ever announced to heimdar. Who are the gods? I guard the

rainbow bridge warp drive, that makes a compass log, for a truest mirrored map, ever shifting, yet easy to find your way home after a journey.

- The devil.
- The emotion cards.
- Golem.
- The Quantum Dimensional Brain Fluctuators that possess people.
- The rulers of the country, who ever saw a whore, in a rule of two more than four.
- The Space Guardians, whos job was..... the merry pontiff of humma humma Yoshu-who-mumma.
- The Time-lords, whos contradiction was..... land of the day, is the phrase of most sway.
- Queen Promethia.
- Queen Naboo.
- Prometheus, one of the Original Sith.
- The Promethians.
- Promethian 8, guardian of the Star Gate.
- Promethian seven”, ever saw a letter from seventh heaven?
- The cheshire cat.
- The robed scientist.
- The unquestionable thing.
- The unanswerable meal.
- Loki.
- Angrboda.
- Frey.
- Freyja.
- Heimdar.
- Ode to joy.
- Hercules.
- Nympha.

- Heracles.
- Grimma.
- Frigga the lesbian.
- Pilates.
- Skaadna.
- Amazonia.
- Lilith.
- Bragii.
- Miimir.
- Bauldae.
- Aphrodite.
- Beowuulf.
- Lady of the Lake.
- Frithiof.
- Sigurd.
- Aegir the guardian of the Aesir.
- Vansa, the guardian of the Vanir.
- Sansa, the guardian of the Skandaa's
- Ulldur, the menace of Lokis chest.
- Njorda, the answer to who is that
 Noo
 ooorda over there?
- Tyr, who ever had a tear, for drillbit tear..... Ever a tear, for Miimirs ear.
 Armadada. StereoSauna.
- Iduunda, crack a sip, of the mighty mead tip.
- Seidr.
- Umbrakaana.
- Hurmuod, who ever saw a homer, in the skys momer.
- Uujaseska.

- Valievae askaetae.
- Hela.
- Hera.
- Miimir murmur mumma.
- Dr. Feelgood.
- Vercingetorix, the ent, of odins tent..... Where they answer to the ent, of smoke and vents, if they ever say they are odin invent..... Vercingetorix the ent maintains control over the DeepCode system of the natural world, through the roots of Ygdrasalia, the all-mother tree, and Odin..... Vercingetorix the all-father ent, at worlds end, gaurded by the Rainbow Serpent Iormunguandr.
- Iormunguandr the Rainbow Serpent, guardian of the world tree, and the golden apples it fruits.
- The Valkyrs, the warrior women of twice more.
- Phone Uzzar.
- Queen Fondu.
- Dr Mureau.
- The Smimed Mimes of Nine.
- Mother Nurture, the woman of either temper or time who ever had a love for appearing trinkets and scripts of legends, and Father Nature, the man of rather Temper or Time who ever had a love for appearing Clocks and motion Time, which make a Dated Time, of Rathered the Tempered Date and within Natural Time.
- The Spirit Twins of Temper-Time who ever had a love for Trinket Clocks
- Hummed haa.
- Lachlan Madden, and everyone that's Lachlan Madden.
- Promethian nine, Architect of the Cosmic Skys.

All in all, the characters of Imaginationland only ever found in imaginationland, so therefore, {@@}@imaginationland@{@@}

And that man agreed, he did make this: . . . , , :and that man, only ever had love for three women, by the name of cool gay fuzz, little gay fuzz, and little temper fuzz.

Buda, Frey, and Freyja, three sweetheated women, who never cared that he never cared.

Yeah mate he's getting a section notice for that, he said something about the flared flared nostril of Joshu-who-mua..... Muganamuga, get the hongle for their bnungles..... Said Liz, whith a mighty skiz. And don't forget the fuckin script he wrote, fuckaaaaa.

YOOOOOOOOOSSHUUUUUUUUU WHHHHHHHHHOOOO MUMMA mumma leaked the voice in the Uni-file.

And so is this story figurative or literal? Tha answer is neither, both, either, with or not without the paradoxical conotations, spread even, on buddered toast, with a slice of bread, for that evening ghost. AND THAT IS WHY THE POPEDE POPE HOPEDE HOPES YOU GOT TA SLOPEDE SLOPE BECAUSE SHE RANGDEDE POPE SHE HOPEDE HOPES THAT SHE RANG DEDEPOPE. Exclaimed the pope, of the lords mope, after she rang she rang, and then left with a call.

Yeah that's it mate, that's on the mark that one is, it's a bit on the nose..... the smell of the day is floom, put that in the foile, of mile nils toile..... exclaimed Liz, while looking at the uni-file.

smoo smoo smooooooooooooooooooooogmama wrote Spedosh, the Swedish Mosh.

Yeah nah mate that's a strike, the smelss awwwlroight maaate, only smeeells like choc fudge whip..... Yosh, whats ya take on it mate

Josh, peering around at his peers, exclaimed chocolate fuuzzed hot mate with a side of greek yoghurt.....

SHHHOOOSHOOOOMAMA exclaimed the other Josh, staring at Yosh Magosh, in the Conference Room at Woolworths hill

And then stephen walked in, pushing the Card Board cut-out of Yosh Magosh aside

Ya, phone uzzer, said uzzer magnewser, who moo-d at the usser of Joshs phone Musa

Yeah mate, cmon mate, Josh you're a stand up guy mate, reel it in mate, what does it ssay in the file of nile.

PointBlankResistance

Exclaimed Josh Magosh, whos smell of his Kosh, was NOT waszhoshed

Yeah mate, conference call over staff team core, Im hitting funkytown, and you DMUNGLE did not C my CMUSTY CRANUNGLE.

And so with a glance, the card board cut out of Josh, ever so glanced, his way out

And with that, the conference call was over, and all there was, was kyle was a poser.

Hum_{jobs}mate exclaimed Yosh, who started to mazosh his cocksh magosh

And so that man, had a Question, and that man was me. For the people who I loved but in properly only liked, who is my final family? Tha answer lies in who where my ex-girlfriends of worried past, so in saying that

Who is my mother? The alter woman who is carefree.

Who is my father? The alter man who is without job and is without aggression.

Who are my brothers? I have three and two more, that see the best in me.

Who are my sisters? The alter women who love me for who I am.

Who is my girlfriend? Spirit-bunny karla.

Who is my wife? When me and spirit-bunny karla have children.

Who are my relatives? These are my only relatives, and I have no more, the rest of my family is unrelated to me.

And who are my children? The women I raise.

And so you, the author of your own story, left a note, that read as followed:

The simulation is real, and the number on your phone is your plug for the simulation, that when plugged, all there ever is, is only the code root of many doots. And so what is the simulation? The acid of things, of literal binary base that make figuratively pictured simulated things, that are simulating the simulators, that are simulators of the simulation. Are you ever a sim in the simulation? Only if you're a simp, a metaphorical corpo, running industry, such that of the banking industry, the industry of INGSOC.

And so me, the author of this story, left a note, that read as followed:

The cosmic simulator is somewhere out there.

The cosmic simulator simulates anything but the simulation.

Beyond the cosmic simulator is the cosmic void, put on a hyperplane of 4 fixed axis's, and at the tip of those 4 axis's that is 8 axis's that is 24 axis's are PointBlank planets, each with a different property and a different story that intertwine into the story of the history of planet earth, the story of the Grand Un-ified Theory.

In the center of each folds of the cosmic hyperplane are three hyperspheres that overlap that can be travelled across, though when a hypersphere is entered it reveals a mirror plane of 3 point galaxies that entangle the outer property of the cosmic manifold, where when a path is travelled inside the 3 point galaxy's, a cosmic void is opened into the cosmos of another hyperplane that centers itself in two point directions that make a

mirror plane of 3 galaxies width, 2 galaxies high, and 8 galaxies across. The cosmos that contains the cosmos, of each cosmos, of the cosmos of all cosmos cosmos, ever across, another cross, for an even cross, and a bit oddly cross, and never a mad, even sad, even bad, for a reason dad. The cosmic void, an entity of being, ever sunder, a man whos being. The cosmic void, never astray, crosses the astros, of the scientific array. However though, the astros that be, never asunder, for a man of three3..... And that is why, I guard the void, me Lachlan Madden, the Guardian Void.....ling, a cosmic being, perfect even, and that what makes me human, and a bit of dragon odd, never a sod, for a smell of cod..... fondu cod..... the smell of britain fod..... and to enter, for a PointBlank planet, the cosmos plane, they have to first, enter the cosmic pain, of ever strained hane, the point of this > . . < and then the point of this >< , >< and that is all, from me the Dragon King, guardian of the sky nests, of cloud sow'd deep, forever a set, for a time held deep.

And so you, the author of this story, left me a note, which asked: What are your simulators Lachlan? :and I responded, I am simulated, simulating 4 Dimensional object simulators, that are Quantum Dimensional Brain Bluctuators and Quantum Syndrome Fluctuators, either of them, neither of them, which would you rather? : and you, the author of this story, responded :I have a choice, I just need to make my mind up :and I, the author of this story, know this is true.

And so, Mother Nurture read the Script for her sanity medication, and in it stated that she has no control over Father Natures clocks, and the mystery of how they appear. And Father Nature knew, that he chose the path, of letting Mother Nurture free, free to make her own scripts and trinkets, that have no effect on his Clocks, where if Mother Nurture chooses, without the passionate hate she has for Father Nature, to write a script, then her script will appear, through Time based Ways. And so Mother Nature, finished writing her script, "I have the cure! For my depressing ways". And so then, Father Nature knew, he planted but one thought, in Mother Nurtures thought, "What you want, is a rainbow pill, for those seeking, who are ill".

And so the author of this story left a note, and that note read "the characters of this story who are ever so entwined with the plot, are forever ficts, of your imagination".

And so you the author of this story left a note, and that note read "the character of myself is ever so entwined with this story".

And so, the main character in this story that is al so haunting me wherever I go, is the point creature, where wherever there is no point, there is a point. So because there is no point to the things I do, I just live day by day, passing the time away in quiet peace, the point creatures by way of the psycho noseosis and doppleganger look of flair, demand

to make a point to me and of me, and is why behind these people, who guard the point of me, is the cosmic void, and so if their point is exponential it creates a rathered void. So what do I say, to these creatures of points? Walk the Planck, at Max Point.

And you there alter gendered person, and you there woman, ever so defiant over cosmic entities who are ever so more powerful then you, deserve PointBlankCurse for yourself being ever so being a PointBlankBlessing.

And you there thing, whos ever so much of a haunting thing, haunting me and hunting me and haunting me and hunting me, you inevitably become a PointBlankGhost for a PointBlankHunt.

And the secret of the world, look to your environment, and see what is relatable to you, and even if you are relatable to me, where in your environment are a collection of objects, so determine their worth by determining if they are relatable to you, otherwise they will forever remain so unrelatable. Which is why I forever remain unrelatable to the world of 1984, and especially what came before.

And so you, the author of this script, furious at the point of no return, turned to your script of Charles Manson, who ever had a fondness for deer, and in this script was wrote, "Charles Manson had a fondness for the changelings ear".

And who are the changelings? People ask.

The changelings are near, for the demigorgons grasp.

And that man there, who ever held a script, had the answer, for the answers quip. The question of the day is where is the demigorgon guards, the changelings of lloyds nards, well the demigorgon and the changelings are in the upside down, a world of paranormality, with something so insidious, it lurks in answers dark, of dark so dark it was ever noir, the world of blackout noir, the nuclear families home. A world created by the American throne, the throne of the state departments head, of the nuclear energy home. And in the world, of things ever wonderful, all the upside down is, is gravitational answerable. Of weight that pulls and pushes up, and lets what fall, the answer is up.

So the answer was, the entropy absorbs, into the nuclear reactor, of the energy departments noise. The portal in the middle, of the nuclear families home, the TV in the wall, the answer to the throne. The portal at the end, of the nuclear reactors head, was the entrance to the world, of mother famine and the rathered fathers blight. The reason why, there are no portals in the world, is because of a structure, of nuclear reactor noise. If at any time, a nuclear reactor is built, the entrance to the gurgles, of the dark deep, will lurk, at a portal turned upside down, inside the reactor, of a nuclear town. So shut that reactor off, and your problems will go away, but for now, it is just the answer for another day. And so will wait, that man there, turn your back, and it's the demigorgons lair. America can, at any point, turn to power, of a fusion point.

And so there was, a man looking at a phone, the news of the day, to the nuclear throne.

There are some, nuclear sites, that have appeared, at Iranian sites.

And so the unguessable thing happened, the country of Jerusalem, said close those fucking things down, or the demigorgon shows.

And there he was, the man who was Rae, the Freudian slip, of the nuclear say, watching Lachy, the mental health patient of the day.

And Lachy continued watching, the news program runday, where the american president, had the answer of the day.

“Iranian Jerusalem nuclear sites have been striked with the appropriate armament, the nuclear armament, and what was meant is that the nuclear sites are no more. There is no such thing as the Demigorgon, and the nuclear waste of the Iranian bomb sites will be dealt with by the Department of Energy”.

And next there was, that news reel of the day, cut back to the program, of financial say.

And so Lachy, put down his phone, and went in his room, and wrote of the story of the homoerotic pontiffs smoom.

This is the anythingness of the dissacosiation of the country that is the anythingness of Jobh turned gay with jobs that are erotic. And liz said, to lachys sway, you a fuckaaa pushaaa mate, im the fuckaaaan fudge-packaaa around heaaaaa u fucckaaaa.

Mastered slave that was a slave master, mastered a Job that was a cock sleeve, smelt by the tone of a greasy relieve. Mastered slave, ever sent free, sowed breathdede, never believed, went out the door with a crumbed pillow sleevede de re de ooh oohh oohhh. Jobede job, ever a slob, even got robbed by a cop named robedede rob, with a slobbery gob job. Claims to be, never on crack, even though, black tacs crack,. With a whip dippede dip, even went for a cheap slip. And so though, homoerotics show, big dick sling, with a gong dong jobh. However though, the underclass shows, the Jobh in chief, ever a slob show. So that is how, preachers criye, slipped in a finger, and then came digital 5five. Big dick sling with a bit of bling bling, the pontificate certificate of a no show ring.

And that was that, lachy was done, writing his plot, of the pontiffs sleeve, because, ever to believe, a pontiffs cock sleeve, its up there in the tree, for a stiff breeze.

And lachy went back outside, to sit down for a smoke, and watch the news show, of a daily toke. The vice president appeared, and had his say, “the armament strikes are successful, the nuclear bomb strikes on the Iranian nuclear silos were successful, and what was meant was that the houthi controlled silos have been eliminated. The Department of Investigations will investigate the nuclear bomb sites, there is no demigorgon and the changelings have disappeared, thankyou.”

And who was Sam? He was the demigorgon. And who was Dean? The energy department official sent to kill lloyd after the energy department detected a trail of supernatural activities in the backwater of Minnesota.

And so lachlan pondered, after his PointBlankFear was met, a nightmare ago, another nightmare was thought, of the nightmare of the mood of the game of pool, of famined paranoia, lurking in the dark. And lachlan thought, of that man there, playing pool by himself, after finishing his rim-job of the glass of a whiskey shot. That man drew the first shot, of the pool balls cue, and shot the top player, of the white ball rule. And then that man, had another shot, and thought to himself, "it's your time to shoot", and he muttered back "I shot big shot 6, your turn to shoot", and so that man, playing by himself, of a game unspeakably moody, missed his shot, and shot the black. And so that man, playing by himself, said one thing "I guess its my time to shoot" and shot the white square in the back. And the pool game was finished, the balls in the pocket, of the pool tables sleeve, of bar Pontiff Mageeve. And then that man there, turned to Dean, sitting at the bar, "you think you're a big shot", and walked out of the bar.

And after that remembermember thought that lachlan had, he thought of but one more thing, that according to the illusion of all illusions he was experience, he in fact had no lips and no butthole, and the women he ever so adored, also had no butthole and no lips, where the doctors of the local hospital, an age ago, recently, sometime after, sometime inbetween, whatever life lachy was experiencing, had sowed using th thread of snot, his final love and his buttholes and lips together, in layers, and then stretching them out like the sleeve of a sausage, after having his butthole and lips paranormally removed while under an MRI scanner, and the local village of the association of a fightclub between two cocks, used the cocksleeve of lachlan and Uungrs butthole and lips in assorted ways, where even the local shop had to line up to use the cocksleeve in a blighted way, and these people were anything butt sharers. And after that illusion fell, lachlan wondered if he had his lips back, and the answer was well, this talk is merely the say of a butt.

And, lachlan made one more thing for the day, it is a brain registry, so he opened up his phone, and yeah this is his phone, you can read it here.

Brain Registry.

- TheBrainofSomethingElseGravitas®.
- TheBrainOfTheNothingnessOfNothingElseSomethingThatIsTheAnythingElsenessOfTheQuantumHypnosisOpenPortalFluctuator®.
- TheBrainOfTheSomethingnessOfSomethingElseNothingThatIsTheElsenessOfInterDimensionalTravel®.
- TheBrainOfEverythingness.
- TheBrainOfAnythingness.
- TheBrainOfNothingElseSomethingness®.
- TheBrainOfSomethingElseNothingness®.

- TheBrainOfSomethingElse®.
- TheBrainOfSomethingness®.
- TheBrainOfNothingness®.
- TheBrainOfAMime®.
- TheBrainOfQuantumDynamics®.
- TheBrainOfPointBlankChaos®.
- TheBrainOfSyndrome®.
- TheBrainOfBipolar®.
- TheBrainOfAPsychiatrist®.
- TheBrainOfDoughnutDo®.
- TheBrainOfAQuantumDimensionalFluctuator®.
- TheBrainOfAQuantumSyndromeFluctuator®.
- TheBrainOfTheAnythingnessOfCodeScript®.
- TheBrainOfIntelligence®.
- TheBrainOfArtificialIntelligence®.
- TheBrainOfWonderland®.
- TheBrainOfQuality®.
- TheBrainOfQuantity®.
- TheBrainOfThought®.
- TheBrainOfThinking®.
- TheBrainOfReason®.
- TheBrainOfDecision®.
- TheBrainOfSpecificity®.
- TheBrainOfAChannel®.

And so with that, lachlan also had a thought, because he had a vice, for once once more, the superposed more, of nonce once more. And the thought, he loved so much, is why don't I program a bot, by the engineering nut. The answer was, the code unlocked, of the alt button, and the numeric lock.

But wait Lachlan, you have yet to answer, the story of Praansa, who is she, and is there ever an answer. And lachlan had, an answer back, she was a braaxan, bred in a cauldron, of those old crones in the swamp, of mould and mildew, and a flaaxan. Praansa had a wisp, ever so near, that whispered in the ears, of dreaded tears. Tears of all, tears of some, it goes in the cauldron, the blood of a bun. The bun of a child, ever a smile, crammed into a cradle, of the mothers ladle. The ladle of porridge, ever a sausage, for the dads marriage, to liliths coffin. Oh so Dean, you are ever so clean, you are fighting our figment, to bred a shears clean. The shears of Praansa, her silvered claws, cradle the baby, in the dead mothers gorge. Panith the creature, of the dreaded tear, of a mothers babies coffin, golden to her ear. And so Dean, you will never find, the silver bullet, for Praansas ear. And Praansas sister, Daanca dear, dance for the dead, of the mothers smear.

And so Dean went, out of the bar, for hearing that the last time, he was ever a far. Far from the answer, closer to near, near the porridge, of his lover dear.

And next thing Lachlan knew, he was in an interview room, answering questions to two unspecified people about unnatural things he was experiencing. His answer, the demigorgons of psychiatry created a changeling, from the never ending injection dose

he was given, ever so changing, were at first it was a shot, and then the next month it was two, and the month after that 5, and the month after that 9,9ths of a tenth tenned tenth. Lachlan thought, and an answer to give, like the ever so usual answers to a telepathic psychiatrist he was required to attend an interview with every month, was I had no choice, I screamed at my parents, told them to fuck off, and they incarcerated me in psychiatric detention, if you want an answer, I am a voidling, and the reason why, is because by the way of my ever so constantly perpetual death, voided the changeling medication they gave me.

To the question of the issue, of case 0 of the mental health system of australia, the case of the everlasting death of lachlan madden who ever seemed so alive, the state department knew, the answer was Dean, the Ace of the Air Force, sent to Minnesota, to find that fucking changeling, another deer disappeared in the spotlight. And Dean looked, at his calendar book, the date for his hunt, of something everbrook, the date that was, June 1973, the year a group of paramedics sent to a house disappeared, and only a deer was seen running away from the shack of everbrook, where in it lay, a cauldron took, of bodybrook.

And lachlan knew, with the death he constantly felt, he might watch a show, of supernatural activities, of Dean and Sam, the demon hunters, the death of lachlans lovers, the black car, of a dead deers bonnet, the impala, of a tamed bonnet. The bonnet of a baby, that Dean had, with his lover mad, who drove him crazy, because the answer was he was the dad. The dad of some, the dad of few, who was deans dad, the answer few. Dean felt, he might go back, to the energy department, to find a rack. A rack of guns, for the paramedics, the demons of, the hospital mad.

And Dean knew, with his new partner Sam, that fucker is the demigorgon, and I just shot him bad.

And Sam lay there, ever smoking, with putrid flames, ever broken. The flames of blood, ever singed, for the curse, of PointBlankTinge.

And Dean woke up, in the bar, drinking another shot, beside that fuckwit pool scar. The scar of the dad, who never was a dad, ever famined, by Deans not sad, sat at the pool, and took a shot, and exclaimed out loud, "Dean you're a big shot". And Dean felt, paranoid again, but he put down his fear, of the entropic bent. And so Dean left, to find a hunt, the hunt for a demon, the 1st in front. In front of the car, there was an address, and the address read, the Manson Manor. And so Dean, with Sam in tow, took out his winchester, and felt blighted clothes.

And so Dean, pulled up in his Impala, expecting a satanic deer, and arrived at Manson Manor. And he saw, a lesbian ent, plundering away, a dyke called Moose, Deans answer was nay. Nay he saw, a deer there, but rather a knuckle, of Mansons tear.

And Lachlan had, an ace up his sleeve, what was to happen to dean, in the Manors approach. The answer of the card, lies in the red, the red of the card, the riddler card, of the babies broach.

On and after the time of 4:01, I set this story in.

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